

Original Article

Infant and Young Child Feeding Practices and Nutritional Status of Children in a Selected Rural Community

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Abstract

Background: The period from birth to two years of age is a “critical window” for the promotion of optimal growth, health and behavioural development. Infant and young child feeding practice especially early initiation and exclusive breast feeding for the first six months of life helps young children to ensure the best possible start of their life.

Objective: To assess the infant and young child feeding practices and nutritional status of children below 2 years of age.

Methodology: This cross-sectional study was conducted in Sanmondi Village at Sonargaon Upazilla of Narayanganj district from 1st January 2019 to 30th June 2019. A total 169 under two-year-old children were included in this study. Data were collected from the mothers of the children by face-to-face interview with a semi-structured questionnaire and using physical measurement tools. Breast feeding and complementary feeding practices of the children were evaluated by using recommended schedule of WHO. Nutritional status of children was classified as per WHO child growth standard 2006. SPSS (version 21) was used for data entry and analysis.

Results: Among 169 children, 53 (31.4%) were under 06 months age group. One hundred and one (59.8%) children got breast milk within one hour of birth. Though colostrum was given to 160 (94.7%) of the new-borns but pre-lacteal feeding was still a tradition (16%). Exclusive breast feeding was given in 54 (46.6%) amongst 116 children of 6-23 months age group. Fifty mothers (43.1%) started complementary food timely at 06 completed months (after 180 days) but institution of Minimum Acceptable Diet (MAD) was absent in most 101(87.1%) of the children. Age specific Minimum Dietary Diversity (MDD) and age specific Minimum Meal Frequency (MMF) was present in 48(41.4%) and 100(59.2%) children's food respectively. Underweight, stunting and wasting was present in 57(33.7%), 100(59.2%) and 20(11.8%) children respectively.

Conclusion: Early initiation of breast feeding and especially colostrum feeding was satisfactory but pre lacteal feeding was still practiced in new-borns. Though more than one third children started complementary feeding timely but appropriate complementary feeding was not practiced in majority of children. Nutritional statuses of children were still not up to the mark.

Keywords: IYCF, Nutritional status, Complementary food.

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Introduction

Appropriate feeding practice is essential for survival, development and proper nutritional growth of infant and young children. These practices are collectively known as Infant and Young Child Feeding (IYCF) practices which include breast feeding and complimentary feeding.¹ The period from birth to two years of age is a “critical window” for the promotion of optimal growth, health and behavioural development.² Infant and child feeding practice especially early initiation of breast feeding and exclusive breast feeding for the first six months of life, helps to ensure young children the best possible start of their life. To meet evolving nutritional requirements, infants should receive nutritionally adequate and safe complementary foods from 6 months of age while breast feeding continues for up to two years of age or beyond.³

Early initiation of breastfeeding is extremely important for establishing successful lactation. Ideally, the baby should receive the first breastfeed as soon as possible and preferably within one hour of birth.³ According to Bangladesh Demographic and Health Survey (BDHS) 2014,⁴ in Bangladesh 55% of infant are exclusively breastfed and only 51% of new-born have early initiation of breast feeding within one hour of birth. Continuation of breast feeding up to one year is 87% in Bangladesh.⁴ Cultural practices of pre lacteal foods contribute to the low prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding.⁵ Introducing pre lacteal feeding is a reason for late initiation of breast feeding. Bottle feeding is common in Bangladesh; 22 percent of infants 6-9 months are fed by bottle with a nipple.⁴ In many studies, both in rural and urban areas of Bangladesh have shown widespread improper breast feeding. Bangladesh Breastfeeding Foundation has given its utmost effort on the global initiative of protection, promotion and support of breast feeding.

The complimentary feeding starts when breast milk alone is no longer sufficient to meet the nutritional requirements of infants and therefore other foods and liquids are needed, along with breast milk. According to WHO appropriate complementary feeding of infants and young children should start from the age of six months with continued breastfeeding up to two years or

beyond.⁶ Only 71% of Bangladeshi infants consume appropriate complementary foods by 6 to 8 months of age and often ‘fall off the growth curve’ once complementary feeding begins.⁷ Twenty three percent (23%) of children aged 6-23 months is fed appropriately according to recommended IYCF practices.

Growth rate in human being is maximum during the first year of life.² According to WHO malnutrition plays a vital role for 60% of the 10.9 million deaths annually among children under 5 years of age globally.⁸ In Bangladesh 36 percent of children under 5 are considered to be short for their age or stunted, while 12 percent are severely stunted (below -3 SD). The prevalence of stunting increases with age from 14 percent of children under age 6 months to 46 percent of children 18-23 months and decreases to 38 percent among children 48-59 months.⁴ Rural children are more likely to be stunted than urban children (38 percent compared with 31 percent).⁴ The level of stunting among children under 5 has declined from 51 percent in 2004 to 36 percent in 2014. Fourteen percent of children are considered wasted or too thin for their height and 3 percent are severely wasted.⁴ Wasting peaks at age 9-11 months (20 percent for moderate wasting and 6 percent for severe wasting). Wasting increased to 17 percent in 2007 from 15 percent in 2004. It has then gradually declined to 14 percent in 2014.⁴ Thirty-three percent of children under age 5 are underweight (low weight-for-age), and 8 percent are severely underweight.⁴ One in five children less than 6 months is underweight. At 6-8 months, 16 percent of children are underweight. The rate of underweight continues to increase with age, peaking at 38 percent at age 48-59 months. The level of underweight has declined from 43 percent in 2004 to 33 percent in 2014.

Over the last two decades, national health policy and strategies progressed with significant achievements. As a part of national health policy, Bangladesh government developed National Maternal Health Strategies, which incorporates a broader approach from rights’ perspective for safer motherhood and included in different health and population sector programmes.⁹ Bangladesh government sets target to achieve the 3rd goal of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) by reducing

proportion of stunting among under 5 children from 36.1% to 25% and proportion of underweight in under five children from 32.6 to 20% and wasting 14% to 8% by 2025.¹⁰

This study was done to find out the feeding pattern and nutritional status of under 2 years children along with their mothers. Bangladesh is passing through a transitional period between attaining targets of MDG and SDG. To accomplish the targets, the study can guide the policy makers to think about further steps to be taken.

Materials and methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted in Sanmondi Village at Sonargaon Upazilla of Narayanganj district from 1st January 2019 to 30th June 2019. A total 169 under two-year children were included in this study. Data were collected by face-to-face interview of the mothers of study participants with a semi-structured questionnaire and using physical measurement tools.

Prior to participation, questionnaire was pretested in Mashukanda village of Sonargaon Upazilla. Ethical clearance of the study was taken from Institutional Review Board of Institute of Child and Mother Health. Informed written consent was taken from study participants. House to house visit was done for data collection. Age of the children was determined from Birth Certificate or EPI card or from mother herself. Breast feeding and complementary feeding practices of the children were evaluated by using recommended schedule of WHO. Complementary feeding status of infant was appraised by age specific diversity, type and frequency of food. Nutritional statuses of children were calculated by measuring weight and length/height. Weight was measured by Bathroom scale and length by Infantometer.

Nutritional status of children was classified as per WHO child growth standard 2006 by calculating Weight for age, Height/length for age and Weight for height/length Z-scores. The cut off values was used to categorize underweight, stunting and wasting for children. Socioeconomic status was measured by using Modified Kuppusswami Socioeconomic Scale updated for January 2018. SPSS (version 21) was used for data entry and analysis. Obtained information was presented in tables.

Results

This cross-sectional study was done among 169 children who were under 2 years of age. Amongst 169 children 53 (31.4%) were of less than 6 months, 11 (6.5%) belong to 6-8 months age group, 23 (13.6%) were of 9-11 months age and 82 (48.5%) were 12-23 months age group. One hundred and one (59.8%) of the children are male. Majority of the children (47.9%) belong to upper lower class, followed by Lower middle class (39.6%) and Upper middle class (12.6%).

One hundred and twenty-seven (76%) mothers didn't enter their SSC exam and most of them (98.2%) were housewife. Ninety-two mothers (55%) got married before the age of 18 years and fifty-eight (34.7%) of them also became pregnant before 18 years of age.

One hundred and sixty (94.6%) mothers reported that they gave colostrum to their new-borns. Early initiation of breast feeding within one hour of birth was started in one hundred and one (59.8%) children. Twenty-seven (16%) mothers gave pre-lacteal food to their new-born before breastfeeding. Mothers use formula milk 13 (48.1%), sugar mixed with water 11 (40.7%), honey 3 (11.1) as pre-lacteal food. Among 116 children of 6-23 months age group, exclusive breast feeding was practiced in 54 (46.6%) babies. Mean duration of exclusive breast feeding was 3.73 ± 2.3 months. Thirty-four (64.2%) out of 53 under 6 months children were practicing exclusive breast feeding (Table I).

Among 53 under 6 months of age group children, 19 (35.8%) had extra feeding other than breast milk. Seventeen mothers (32.1%) complain that their children were not getting enough breast milk. Amongst 116 children of 6-23 months 58 (50%) had extra food before their 6 months of age (Table II).

Fifty children (43.1%) started complementary feeding timely at 6 completed months (after 180 days) and 61 (52.9%) of them started before 6 months; only 5 (4.3%) children initiated after 7 months and onwards. Continuation of breast feeding along with complementary feeding is practiced in 100 (86.2%) mothers.

Complementary feeding practices of 6-23 months age group children of Sanmondi village have been shown in Table III. Minimum Dietary Diversity (MDD) was variable in different age group of

children. Complementary food of 68(58.6%) children did not enclose Minimum Dietary Diversity (MDD). It was only 48(41.4%) children who received minimum diverse diet. Most of the children (82.6%) of 9-11 months age group did not get their required number of food group. Minimum Meal Frequency (MMF) was inappropriate in 69(59.5%) children and 47(40.5%) children were fed recommended times as their age. One hundred and one (87.1%) children did not get Minimum Acceptable Diet (MAD). It is minimum (4.3%) in 9-11 months age group (Table III).

Only 32 (27.6%) children used to take Vitamin A rich food, but 93.1% children took Vitamin A capsule along with their vaccination. Junk food is common in 58 (50%) of 6-23 months age group children. Among 169 children, 57(33.7%) were under weight. One hundred (59.2%) children of Sanmondi were found to be stunted. Twenty children (11.8%) had wasting; 12(7.1%) had severe wasting and 8(4.7%) had moderate wasting. Overweight was found 44 (26.03%) children among study participants. Male children were more prone to underweight, stunting and wasting (Table IV). Hygiene status of the caregivers was good in most cases (93.5%). One hundred and twenty-three (72.8%) mothers use soap and water for washing hands (Table V).

Table I*Breastfeeding status of children 0- 23 months*

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Early initiation of breast feeding	101	59.8
Colostrum	106	94.6
Pre-lacteal food	27	16.0
Types of pre-lacteal food (n=27)		
Formula milk	13	48.1
Sugar mixed with water	11	40.7
Honey	3	11.1
Exclusive Breast feeding		
≤6 months(n=53)	34	64.2
6-23 months(n=116)	54	46.6

Table II*Extra food other than breast feeding given in 0-6months children (n=53)*

Types and causes of giving extra food	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Type of extra food		
Formula milk	9	16.9
Cow's milk	7	13.2
Breast milk along with formula milk	3	5.6
Causes of giving extra food		
Insufficiency of breast milk	17	32.1
Breast problem	2	3.7

Table III*Complementary feeding practices of children (6 – 23 months)*

	Minimum Dietary diversity (MDD)		Minimum Meal Frequency (MMF)		Minimum Acceptable Diet (MAD)	
	Present	Absent	Appropriate	Inappropriate	Appropriate	Inappropriate
6-8 months(n=11)	4(36.4)	7(63.6)	5(45.5)	6(54.6)	3(27.3)	8(72.7)
9-11 months(n=23)	4(17.4)	19(82.6)	8(34.8)	15(65.2)	1(4.4)	22(95.7)
12-23 months(n=82)	40(48.8)	42(52.2)	34(41.5)	48(58.5)	11(13.4)	71(86.6)

Table IV*Nutritional Status of Children below 2 years of age*

Sex	Weight for Age n (%)			Height for Age n (%)			Weight for Height n (%)		
	Under weight	Normal	Over weight	Stunting	Normal	Tall	Wasting	Normal	Over weight
Male	36 (21.3)	60 (35.5)	5(2.9)	67(39.6)	31(18.3)	3(1.7)	13(7.7)	59(34.9)	29(17.2)
Female	21(12.4)	36 (21.3)	11(6.5)	33(19.5)	28(16.5)	7(4.1)	7(4.1)	46 (27.2)	15(8.8)
Total	57(33.7)	96(56.8)	16(9.5)	100(59.2)	59(34.9)	10(5.9)	20(11.8)	105(62.1)	44(26.0)

Table V
Hand washing practice of mother and children

Hand washing practices	Categories	Frequency n (%)
Hand washing of children above 6 months of age (n=116)	Good	66 (56.9)
	Not appropriate	50 (43.1)
Hand washing of caregivers (n=169)	Good	157 (93.4)
	Not appropriate	12 (6.5)
Product used for hand washing (n=169)	Only Water	44 (26.0)
	With soap and water	123 (72.8)
	With Ash and water	2 (1.2)

Discussion

The study included 169 children of below 2 years age. In this study, most of the mothers (94.6%) reported that they gave colostrum to their newborns which were consistent with a study conducted in a slum area of Dhaka city.¹¹

One hundred and one (59.8%) mothers started breast feeding to their babies within one hour of birth. This did not correspond with BDHS 2014 findings (51%) and study done by Akhter K et al.¹¹ (45.0%) and M. Selim (24%).¹²

Exclusive breast feeding was practiced in 54 (46.6%) babies of 6-23 months age group. Thirty-four (64.2%) out of 53 under 6 months children were practicing exclusive breast feeding. Mean duration of exclusive breast feeding was 3.73±2.3 months. BDHS 2014 found fifty-five percent (55%) of children under age 6 months are exclusively breastfed and median duration of exclusive breastfeeding is 2.8 months.⁴ Akhter K et al.¹¹ showed 16% of mother breast fed their babies exclusively.

Twenty-seven (16%) mothers gave their new-born pre-lacteal food before giving breastfeeding. According to BDHS 2014, twenty-seven percent (27%) of Bangladeshi children receive a pre-lacteal feed.⁴ Akhter K et al.¹¹ found it in a higher percentage (84%) of new-born.

Among 53 children under 6 months of age, 19 children (35.8%) had extra feeding other than breast milk. Nine babies (16.9%) of them used to give formula feeding and 3(5.6%) children took cow's milk. Amongst 116 children of 6-23 months, 58 (50%) had extra food before their 6 months of age. BDHS 2014 showed that bottle feeding is common in Bangladesh.⁴ It is common (26%) in

children of 4-5 months of age and 22% of infants of 6-9 months are fed with a bottle.

In Sanmondi village, 50(43.1%) children started complementary feeding timely at 6 completed months. BDHS 2014 found that complementary foods were not introduced in a timely fashion for all children in Bangladesh. Seventy percent (70%) of breastfed children aged 6-9 months received complementary foods. And it was 64% in the study of Akhter K et al.¹¹

Among 116 children of 6-23 months, complementary feeding based on recommended IYCF practices was not practiced in 101(87.1%) children. It is higher (23%) in BDHS 2014 reporting. Forty-eight (41.4%) children of Sanmondi received minimum diverse diet and 47(40.5%) children were fed recommended times as their age. BDHS2014 informed that 28 % of children receives the appropriately diverse diet, and 64% of children are fed the recommended number of times with solid or semi-solid foods.⁴

In the present study, only 32 (27.6%) of the children used to take Vitamin A rich food but 93.1% children took Vitamin A capsule along with their vaccination. Forty percent (40%) consume vitamin A-rich fruits and vegetables and sixty two percent (62%) of children found to receive vitamin A supplementation in BDHS 2014 survey.⁴ Among 169 children (0-23 months) of Sanmondi village, 57(33.7%) were under weight, 100(59.2%) were stunted and 20(11.8%) had wasting; 12(7.1%) had severe wasting and 8(4.7%) had moderate wasting. BDHS 2014 reported that among under 5 children, 33% are underweight 8% severely underweight, 36% are stunted, 14% are wasted and 3% are severely wasted. In another study almost more

than half of the children under two years of age, 55.7% were under weight and 42.6% were stunted and 36.5% were wasted.¹¹ Study done in Chittagong Hill Tract showed that the prevalence of underweight and stunting was 56% and 48% respectively.¹³ In a study from India, the overall prevalence of underweight, stunting and wasting was 63.7%, 47.85% and 32.7% correspondingly.¹⁴

Hand washing is an important step in improving hygiene and preventing the spread of disease. Most of the caregivers (93.5%) wash their hands before feeding their children. One hundred and twenty-three (72.8%) mothers use soap and water for washing their hands; BDHS 2014 showed that the availability of a hand washing station that had water and a cleansing agent (including soap) is 37%.

Conclusion

The study was permitted to conclude that early initiation of breast feeding and specially colostrum feeding was satisfactory but pre lacteal feeding was still practiced in new-borns. Though more than one third children obtained complementary feeding at time but appropriate complementary feeding is not practiced in majority of children. Nutritional statuses of children in Sanmondi village were still not up to the mark. The findings of the study suggest that specific efforts are needed to target children and women with provision of basic health care services.

Recommendation:

Proper knowledge regarding importance of exclusive breast feeding and appropriate complementary feeding and its nutritional consequence through frequent and necessary health education can play a significant role in achieving targets of Sustainable Development Goal. Use of available structures and resources to establish a community-based, multi-sector synchronized policy can support nutrition sensitive and nutrition specific interventions.

References:

1. National food policy capacity strengthening program (2013). Guideline For Complimentary Feeding in Bangladesh.
2. Pan American Health Organization and World Health Organization (PAHO & WHO). Guiding Principles for complementary feeding of the breastfeed child. 2003; PAHO & WHO.
3. Ministry of Human Resource development. National Guidelines on Infant and Young Child Feeding (IYCF), Government of India 2004.
4. Bangladesh Demographic and Health Survey (BDHS-2014)
5. Ahmed FU, Rahman ME, Alam MS. Pre-lacteal feeding: influencing factors and relation to establishment of lactation. Bangladesh Med Res Counc Bull. 1996; 22: 60–4.
6. Complementary feeding. Geneva: WHO; 2001.
7. Kabir I, Khanam M, Agho KE, Mihrshahi S, Dibley MJ, Roy SK. Determinants of inappropriate complementary feeding practices in infant and young children in Bangladesh: secondary data analysis of demographic health survey 2007.
8. World Health Organization. Global strategy for infant and young child feeding [A55/15, Anned-16 April 2002], Annex 2, WHO
9. Faruque ASG, Ahmed AMS, Ahmed T, Islam MM, Hossain IM, Roy SK, et al. Nutrition: Basis for Healthy Children and Mother in Bangladesh. JPHN .2008 Sep; 26(3): 325-39
10. Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in Bangladesh: Key Challenges and Missing Links: Focus should be on Internal Resource Mobilization and Effective Democratic Institutions | Social Watch [Internet]. Socialwatch.org. 2019 [cited 17 June 2019]. Available from: <http://www.socialwatch.org/node/18086>
11. Akhtar K, Haque ME, Islam MZ, Yusuf MA, Sharif AR, Ahsan AI. Feeding Pattern and Nutritional Status of Under Two Years Slum Children J Shaheed Suhrawardy Med Coll, 2012; 4(1):3-6
12. Selim M, Mita SA, Uddin MN, Jahan NWB, Ali MZ, Rahman MM, Haque MA. Infant and Young Child Feeding Practices up to Two Years of Age and Their Nutritional Status. Bangladesh Medical Journal 2012 Vol. 41 No.1
13. Akhter N, Torlesse H, Pee Sde, Ibrahim QIU, Stallkamp G, Panagides D, Bloem MW. Nutritional Status of Young Children and Their Mothers in Chittagong Hill Tracts, Bangladesh. 2003 Dec; P57(172). [Web: <http://www.icddrb.org/publication>]
14. Bisai S, Bose K, Dikshit S. Under-nutrition among slum children aged 3-6 years in Midnapore town, India. The Internet Journal of Biological Anthropology 2009;2 (2): 26-29.

Original Article

Childhood Neurodevelopmental Impairment and Disability in a Selected Rural Area of Bangladesh

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Abstract

Background: Impairment and disability are seen as a continuum of functional deterioration of activities. There is increasing evidence that many individuals with neurodevelopmental impairment/disability accumulate problems over time in a cascading and cumulative manner. So, identifying children with neurodevelopmental problems is very important.

Objective: To determine the prevalence of neurodevelopmental impairments and disabilities among children (0-18 years) in a selected rural area of Bangladesh.

Methods: This population-based survey was conducted between January–June 2019 using a cross-sectional two-stage design. At Stage-1 preliminary door to door survey was done by data collectors with 'Household form' and 'Ten Questions Plus (TQP) form'. At Stage-2, diagnostic workout was conducted with Rapid Neuro-Developmental Assessment (RNDA) tools by a professional team on all TQP-positive and 10% TQP-negative children.

Results: Total 86 children were identified with neurodevelopmental impairments or disabilities (NDI/NDD) with slight male preponderance and age range 15 months to 15 years. About half of them had single NDI/NDD and one-fourth had >2 NDDs. Prevalence of motor difficulty was found 14.8/1000, visual problem 10.5/1000, impaired hearing 6.8/1000, speech problem 17.6/1000, cognitive delay 42.1/1000 and seizure in 13.6/1000 children. Spastic Cerebral Palsy was commonest motor disability. The top two neuro-impairment/disabilities by domain were cognitive delay followed by speech problem.

Conclusion: This survey showed a high prevalence of NDI/NDD which might reflect a part of national NDI/NDD burden-estimate. The findings elaborated the need as well as poor availability of the special-need services in the rural areas, and the info might help in the necessary reformation of local healthcare system.

Key words: Neurodevelopmental disability, Ten question plus form, Childhood.

Introduction:

Neurodevelopmental impairments and disabilities comprise a spectrum of prevalent disorders that affect social, communication, activity, attention, motor coordination and literacy skills.¹ They frequently co-occur, predominantly persist

throughout life and are commonly associated with adverse psychosocial outcomes for both the individual and their family. The burden associated with these problems is considerable, yet arguably underestimated.

In neurodevelopmental disabilities, the development of the central nervous system is disturbed. The dysfunction of developmental brain can be manifested as impaired motor function, sensory audiovisual problems or learning difficulties with verbal or non-verbal communication. There is no fixed single cause of these impairments/delays, but many factors may contribute to it by offering windows of vulnerability for adverse effects on healthy neurodevelopment.

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